

Paper ID

Impact of Physical Internet and on-the-fly reallocation on last mile parcel delivery performance: A case study approach**Lavanya Meherishi^{1*}, Camill Harter¹, David Ciprés², José Luis López², Kostas Zavitsas³**

1. Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam, Netherlands

2. Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón, Spain

3. VLTN, Belgium

*meherishi@rsm.nl

Abstract

This research paper assesses the impact of collaborative transport strategies on last mile deliveries through a Physical Internet vision and the use of an urban digital twin. The study uses a simulated environment to analyze the effects of different transport and collaboration strategies on operational, economic, and environmental indicators. The results show that collaborative transport strategies can significantly improve last mile delivery performance, reducing delivery times, costs, and emissions. The paper concludes that the use of urban digital twin in combination with collaborative transport strategies can be an effective approach to optimize last mile deliveries and promote sustainable urban logistics. Also, the research provides valuable insights for urban planners and logistics companies looking to optimize last mile delivery operations in cities.

Keywords:

Physical internet, digital twin, collaboration, order sharing, fleet sharing

Introduction

In Last Mile Delivery (LMD), the design of the delivery rounds involves the pairing of each parcel delivery location with a vehicle, while respecting the time and operational constraints of the customer and vehicle drivers. Typically, in the last-mile, parcels located at central warehouses or distribution centres need to be distributed to customer locations all around the city. Urban LMD is typically associated with not only high uncertainty due to the busy city environment but also high operational costs as it accounts for around 30% of operators' costs (DfT, 2019) namely fuel, rental fee of consolidation centres, staff salaries, vehicle purchase, and other logistics' fixed costs such as insurance and maintenance. Furthermore, about 50% of the total delivery tour time in urban LMDs is not spent driving but spent while the vehicle is parked and the handover of orders to the final customers takes place (GLA (2017), Allen et al. (2018)). In other words, urban delivery uncertainty arises from urban road traffic, parking spot availability as well as during the handover process.

The delivery rounds are typically designed using the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) and its variants,

a popular operations research problem with wide applicability, that has been extensively researched and documented in the literature since 1960s. The VRP is a well-known NP-hard problem because it includes the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) as a special case (Garey and Johnson (1979)). To address large real-world delivery round design instances, heuristics and approximate methods are typically used for identifying near optimal solutions. Furthermore, the mathematically optimized solution is frequently found to lack the implicit knowledge of the urban environment and its limitations, seasoned delivery drivers have. Recent advances in improving the accuracy of the VRP utilizing historical data and Machine Learning, attempt to address this issue (Merchan et al. (2022)).

Current practices in LMD design and implementation are limited both by the lack of evidence as well as the unwillingness of operations to alter existing practices and go through the risk of changing processes that work. This paper focuses on the integration of collaborative and Physical Internet principles in LMD operations with the objective of enabling efficient urban logistics. Through the implementation of various technologies such as Blockchain and IoT to aid the transition towards a PI paradigm, the results explicitly show that collaboration on orders and fleets belonging to competing companies can not only help lower costs, thereby contributing to a company's bottom line, but also help reduce the carbon footprint for each company participating in the collaboration. This research has been conducted as part of the PLANET project (Progress towards Federated Logistics through the Integration of TEN-T into A Global Trade Network). PLANET is an EU funded project addressing the challenges of assessing the impact of emerging global trade corridors on the TEN-T network and ensuring effective integration of the European to the Global Network by focusing on two key pillars: Understanding and Assimilating Global, Geopolitical, Trade and Economic Imperatives and Leveraging Technological Advancements and New Logistics Concepts. The present work addresses PLANET's objective to enable vertical integration through disruptive concepts and technologies.

Literature review

Table 1 Review of key extant literature

	Transportation Modes			Technology	T&L innovations	UCC	Collaboration Type		Methodology	Objective Type
	Trucks	E-vans	E-bikes				Carrier Fleet Capacity Sharing	Carrier Order Sharing		
Liu et al. (2010)	✓							✓	LSO	Empty vehicle moves (Min)
Handaku and Lau (2016)	✓				Platform	✓		✓	GT	CS(Max)
Wang et al. (2017)	✓				Platform			✓	LSO	P(Max) & fair P sharing
Chabot et al. (2018)	✓							✓	LSO	Costs,Emissions (Min)
Los et al. (2020)	✓				Platform	✓		✓	GT	Service, Profit (Max), Time (Min)
Guo et al. (2021)	✓				Reshuffling, Platform	✓		✓	LSO, GT	Costs,Emissions (Min)
McLeod et al. (2021)	✓		✓	GPS		✓		✓	LSO	Costs,Emissions (Min)
Current Study	✓	✓	✓	BC,IoT,	Reshuffling, PI enabled platform	✓	✓	✓	LSO	Costs (Min)

CS: Cost Savings, GT: Game Theory, LSO: Large Scale Optimization, Max: Maximization, Min: Minimization, P: Profit, BC: Block Chain, PI: Physical Internet, IoT: Internet of Things

Table 1 highlights the key articles reviewed in the field of carrier collaborations in last-mile deliveries. As can be seen from the table, there is a lack of studies which explicitly address the use of different technology and logistics innovations for efficient collaboration between carriers. More specifically, even though studies such as Handoko and Lao (2016), Los et al. (2020), and Guo et al. (2021) suggest the use of platforms to negotiate and allocate orders and capacity among participating carriers, the approach to sharing via collaboration is not analyzed. Also, the number of studies which consider the sharing of carrier’s proprietary vehicle capacity is limited. It is commonly assumed that with the establishment and use of urban consolidation centres (UCC), the responsibility of arranging fleet capacity for last mile deliveries is of the UCC operator (e.g., Handoko and Lao (2016), McLeod et al. (2021)). Furthermore, even though studies such as Chabot et al. (2018), Guo et al. (2021), and McLeod et al. (2021) consider the objective of minimizing emissions in the system considered, they do not capture the impact of using greener transportation options such as E-vans and E-bikes for last mile deliveries instead. This current study aims at filling the gaps highlighted above. The main research questions of this study are delineated below:

- T&L innovation impact. Does a Physical Internet strategy where carriers share orders and fleet capacity improve vehicle fill rates for each participating carrier?
- Fleet sizing. Can order and fleet sharing strategies improve customer service levels while allowing for a reduction of fleet size?
- Urban consolidation centres. To what extent do additional UCCs in the system impact service level performance?
- Green vehicles. Can electric vehicles be deployed to reduce emissions without impairing service performance?

Methodology

Inspired by the metaphor of Digital Internet, the Physical Internet (PI) aims to integrate logistics networks into an open and interconnected global system through standard containers and routing protocols (Ballot and Montreuil (2014)). The Physical Internet is a global logistics system in which products are transported in standardized, modular containers as efficiently and effortlessly as in the case of Digital Internet transferring information between servers. Physical Internet is an open framework also from the point of view of the use of the resources. The use of open warehouses and transport networks looks for a systemic load consolidation and optimization in which the capacity in the logistics sites and transport networks could be more available for the use of stakeholders in a more optimized way: reducing energy consumption, environmental emissions, and economic cost.

Under this paradigm and within the framework of the PLANET project, an urban digital twin has been developed to assess the impact of collaborative transport strategies on last mile deliveries. Through this microscopic simulation model, with strategic focus on urban logistics and commitment to the Physical Internet vision, answers are provided to the main research questions of this study, allowing users to make decisions based on the results of applying what-if scenarios.

The digital twin has been built in four steps:

1. First, with a process diagramming approach, the current operations and processes of last mile distribution have been studied, including a review of the most common available or exchanged information by logistics operators.
2. Second, based on this information, a data model has been developed on which to collect standardized information from different logistics operators. This data model includes key information to characterize orders, hubs, and vehicles.
3. Third, the simulation model has been developed using Agent Based Modelling (ABM) techniques, matching the behaviour of the agents in the simulation model to the current last mile distribution processes.
4. Finally, an input and output data template has been designed, so that the simulation model allows users to explore the results under different configurations or scenarios.

The simulation model has been built using multi-agent simulation techniques. The main components in the model are:

- Hubs: hubs are the logistics nodes from where vehicles and orders depart. The properties that define a hub are its unique identifier, name, position (latitude and longitude) and time windows.
- Orders: orders are the customer demand. The properties that define an order are its unique identifier, position (latitude and longitude), delivery time window, number of packages, weight, departure hub and assigned tour.
- Tours: tours are the different routes that vehicles travel to complete orders. The properties that define a tour are its unique identifier, assigned vehicle and departure time.

- Transports: transports travel the routes delivering and picking up orders. The properties that define a transport are its unique identifier, capacity (weight and volume), speed, costs (activation, distance, time...) and emissions.

The model's agents have their own states, can make intelligent decisions, communicate with each other, or respond to changes and parameters. An example of the state chart for a delivery vehicle (transport agent) is shown in Figure 1. The agent can be in a certain state (yellow blocks) and change state when a transition (black arrows) is triggered. This can happen when a certain time passes, when the agent reaches its destination, when a certain condition is met or when a message is received from another agent.

Figure 1 Transport agent state chart

The main view of the digital twin is shown in Figure 2. During the simulation run, the main screen displays the orders grouped by routes, and the movement of delivery vehicles.

Figure 2 Main view of the urban digital twin

Figure 3 shows the stats panel where the statistics collected dynamically during the simulation are gathered and displayed. Some examples are distance travelled, emissions, costs, orders completed on time, lead times or fill rate.

Figure 3 Stats view of the urban digital twin

A collaborative parcel reshuffling algorithm is executed whenever a significant delay arises in the LMD plan being implemented. For example, in Madrid delivery vehicles are prohibited for making parcel deliveries past 9pm. If a vehicle is expected to do so, it has to return with any undelivered parcels to hub, that will be scheduled for delivery the following day. To address this challenge operators frequently seek to merge deliveries withing their own fleet manually. The collaborative parcel reshuffling algorithm automates and optimises the procedure and enables collaboration between other LMD operations operating in proximity. The process initially filters all delivery rounds registered in the platform in terms of their estimated time of completion, to eventually identify the ones with higher availability. The round centroid is then calculated automatically considering all pending delivery locations for each round separately, to identify vehicles operating in close proximity. Once the optimal help round has been identified, the task of reshuffling the pending parcels is initiated that aims to identify which of the pending parcels of the two rounds should be delivered by which vehicle, to alleviate overall delivery delays. The late running round needs to share some of its load with the helping round, however up to this point it is not clear which ones should be transferred. A Machine Learning clustering algorithm proposed by Lin et al. (2022) that produces equal cluster sizes utilizing constrained balancing is applied to the dataset, that divides the pending delivery parcels to two roughly equal in size clusters using their centroids. The algorithm compulsorily assigns all nodes to one of the two clusters, leaving no nodes unassigned. The clustering is performed using a travel-time matrix as the criterion of vector separation of a node to the cluster centroid as obtained using Open Street Maps API.

The output of the clustering algorithm is a tag for each node of the population, that corresponds to a unique delivery round. Each tag is then associated to each of the two delivery rounds, by using a linear optimization model that minimizes the number of parcels to be transferred to the help vehicle. The parcels are therefore, classified into the ones remaining in the late running round, the ones remaining in the help round, and the ones moving from the late running round to the help round.

To complete the two-vehicle collaboration, it is required to convert that information to instructions for the two transport drivers. New routes for both vehicles are designed, that incorporate a meeting point where the parcel exchange will take place, and the information on which parcels require to be transferred from the one van to the other are made available to the drivers.

Results and discussion

To address the main research questions of this paper, a scenario-based case study has been constructed in the city of Madrid (Spain). The main assumptions of the scenarios are: three logistics companies operate in the city centre and hundreds of orders synthetically generated based on real demand data must be delivered during a normal day of operation. A description of each of the simulation scenarios

is presented in the following subsections.

Scenario 1. As-is

In the baseline scenario, the three companies operate in the centre of the city in the traditional, non-collaborative manner. Each company has a fleet of three conventional delivery vehicles, which start their routes from their company's hub located on the outskirts of the city, as shown in Figure 4 (left). The distribution of demand among the companies, represented by the different colours are also shown in Figure 4 (right).

Figure 4 Companies' hub location and demand distribution

Scenario 2. Collaborative urban hubs

In this scenario, collaborative urban consolidation hubs are implemented to facilitate collaborative cargo distribution using the Physical Internet approach. These centers act as hubs for receiving and sorting parcels from the three companies, standardizing the cargo containers and transportation modes, and redistributing them to their respective destinations. By centralizing the distribution process in this way, the system aims to reduce traffic congestion and emissions, as well as increase the efficiency of delivery operations. The simulation tracks the flow of goods through the centers and measure the impact on logistics and transportation in the area. Additionally, it also considers the cost-effectiveness and sustainability of the consolidated distribution model and how it aligns with the Physical Internet concept.

Scenario 3. Collaborative urban hubs + e-vehicles

This scenario aims to show the potential for using electric vehicles and cargo bikes in collaborative cargo distribution networks and the benefits it can bring in terms of sustainability and urban logistics. The urban consolidation centres established in the previous scenario are still being used to facilitate collaborative cargo distribution using the Physical Internet approach. However, in this scenario, traditional delivery vehicles are replaced with electric vehicles (EVs) and cargo bikes, as shown in

Figure 5. This change in transportation mode is aimed at reducing the environmental impact of cargo distribution and increasing the sustainability of the logistics and supply chain network.

The simulation tracks the performance of the EV and cargo bike fleet, including factors such as range, speed, and cost-effectiveness, as well as their impact on reducing emissions. Additionally, the simulation measures the impact of using cargo bikes in urban areas, such as the reduced traffic congestion and improved accessibility in densely populated areas.

Figure 5 Collaborative urban hubs location and order-hub assignment

Results

Table 2 shows the results after running the simulations corresponding to each of the scenarios. To compare the results, operational, economic, and environmental indicators have been defined.

Table 2 Scenarios' results

KPI	S1. As-is	S2. Collaborative Urban Hubs	S3. Collaboration + e-Vehicles
Distance (km)	585 km	210km	180 km
Emissions (kg CO2)	285 kg	150 kg	0 kg
Cost (€)	3080 €	2780 €	2230 €
Fill rate (%)	20 %	35%	50 %
Lead Time (h)	6 h	5.5 h	5 h
Vehicles	9 conventional vans	6 conventional vans	3 e-Vans + 5 cargo bikes

Compared to the baseline scenario, not only does collaboration lead to a reduction in distance traveled and emissions, but it also results in a decrease in the fleet size. This, in turn, improves the fill rate of vehicles, meaning that a smaller number of vehicles are able to serve the same demand, resulting in more efficient use of the resources of each company. Furthermore, the results also show that collaboration leads to a decrease in fixed costs, such as vehicle activation, as well as variable costs, such as fuel and driver expenses. This suggests that collaboration not only improves environmental performance, but also results in better delivery performance for the system as a whole. In scenario 3, the use of electric vehicles results in a complete elimination of emissions. This demonstrates that transitioning to alternative fuel vehicles can effectively reduce the environmental impact of transportation systems while maintaining or improving performance in other areas, such as cost savings.

Conclusion and future directions

In conclusion, this research paper has assessed the impact of collaborative transport strategies on last mile deliveries through a Physical Internet vision and the use of an urban digital twin. Through the use of a simulated environment, the study has analyzed the effects of different transport and collaboration strategies on operational, economic, and environmental indicators. The results have shown that collaborative transport strategies can significantly improve last mile delivery performance, reducing delivery times, costs, and emissions.

The use of an urban digital twin in combination with collaborative transport strategies has been shown to be an effective approach to optimize last mile deliveries and promote sustainable urban logistics. This research provides valuable insights for urban planners and logistics companies looking to optimize last mile delivery operations in cities. The Physical Internet vision, which aims to optimize the use of resources and infrastructure in logistics, is particularly relevant in the context of last mile delivery. The collaboration and coordination among different actors in the logistics chain can lead to

more efficient and sustainable operations.

One of the main challenges for the implementation of collaborative transport strategies is the sharing of data among companies. To mitigate this challenge, the use of secure and anonymous data sharing mechanisms such as blockchain can be considered. Blockchain technology allows for the secure and anonymous sharing of data among different actors, which can help to overcome the trust and privacy issues associated with data sharing.

It is important to note that the results of this study are based on a simulated environment, and further research is needed to validate the findings in real-world scenarios. Nonetheless, the insights gained from this research can be used to inform the development of collaborative transport strategies and the implementation of urban digital twin in the logistics industry. By addressing the challenges faced in last mile delivery, the adoption of these approaches can lead to more efficient, cost-effective, and sustainable urban logistics.

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